

CONTRIBUTIONS OF AFRICAN RELIGION TO SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION IN NATION BUILDING

Eze Okorie Igodo^{1*}

¹ Department of Religious Studies, Ebonyi State College of Education, Ikwo, Nigeria

* ezeokorie400@gmail.com; 08073126384

Abstract

The act of nation building is a great task that requires a lot of commitment, sacrifice and above all, sustainable development and innovation. Unless the leaders and followers have the indomitable will to endure some personal inconveniences and sincerely get committed to the business of nation building, Nigeria's problem may not be solved. Sustainable development and innovation are not only integral but crucial for nation building. It enables countries to achieve economic growth, social progress and environmental protection. With politics of virtue, a leader may not bring about the necessary changes that would benefit the general public. In view of this, it has become imperative to explore the input made so far by African religion in its quest to contribute to sustainable development and innovation in nation building. By promoting the values and practices of African religion, a strong, stable and prosperous nation can be built. Descriptive research design was employed in data collection and analysis. Nations can actually achieve long-term prosperity, social justice and environmental protection by integrating sustainable development and innovation.

1 Introduction

Nation building is a very important project that comes with sustainable development and innovation. Any nation aspiring for greatness must as a matter of urgency inculcate into its national development programmes that are achievable and sustainable. To make this happen, the affairs of the nation will have to be run in such a way as to inspire the people to think and act in a manner that generates loyalty and commitment to national development. In view of this, leaders have to be innovative and committed to actions and policies that engender sustainable development in nation building. African religious leaders and institutions often play vital roles in promoting peace reconciliation and conflict resolution which support sustainable development goals. In the same vein, interfaith dialogue and cooperation between African religion and other religions promote understanding among various religious groups which goes a long way to supporting nation building and sustainable development. African religion more than any other faith supports networks, social cohesion, fosters community engagement and promotes collective well being and development. In the words of Oloyede (cited by Akindele, 2010), the history of the world has been described as the history of religion and man is not just a political animal as Aristotle argued but also a religious being. This is against the backdrop that since creation, human beings have been shaped and their destiny determined by religion. Therefore, religion has continued to be a powerful tool in influencing and determining not only the attitudinal behavior of man but also the future of mankind especially in the religiously polarized societies of Africa and the world in general. In other words, we have to either allow religion to shape us or we shape religion to achieve our purposes of existence.

Ake (1988) recalls that the influence of African religious and cultural beliefs as they affect the implementation of the various goals of development remains largely under researched and unaddressed despite the

need for a home grown model of self reliant development which can come about if we learn to build on the indigenous. The imperative of culture and tradition in any development agenda has equally been expressed by Dia (cited by Akindele, 2010) when he said that the most promising way to overcome the shortcomings of the state system and its alien formal institutions in Africa is to recognize functional and structural disconnect between the informal indigenous institutions rooted in the region's history and culture and formal institutions mostly transplanted from outside. The reason for this according to Dia (cited by Awka, 2009) is to ensure a reconnect between the state and civic society and to identify opportunities within indigenous institutions for building a pluralistic and participatory form of governance and development.

2 Conceptual Clarification of African Religion

The term "African Religion" subsumes African Traditional Religion whereas African Traditional Religion is a subset of African Religion. African Religion is broader in meaning and encompasses African Traditional Religion in modern expressions of faith because it has adapted and contextualized other religions such as Christianity and Islam within African cultures, while African Traditional Religion refers to the pre-colonial belief system and practices that is native to Africa. It is a religion that embraces and embodies all the customs, culture and traditions of African people practiced in various communities and tribes in Africa. It is an organized belief system which places emphasis on virtues, values and morals. Ugwu (2001) adds that they have leaders or officials whose roles are indispensable as far as the beliefs and practices of this religion are concerned. It is a legacy that has been handed down to the people from their ancestors. This religion has dominated the thinking of Africans such that it has shaped their culture, their social life, their political organizations and economic activities. In his study of African religion, Mbiti (1975) observed that just like every other religion, African religion has elements that are interconnected and are seen to be working together to define life, ethics and community, not as separate doctrines but as a dynamic system woven into existence. These elements as he noted are not isolated but reveal how Africans experience the divine and maintain harmony in their daily lives, emphasizing community relationships and tradition. These elements which constitute the focus of this study are further compressed into three major interconnected parts namely beliefs, practices and value systems.

Beliefs

These reflect the way Africans think about the universe and their attitude towards life. It portrays their holistic worldview, that is, there is no clear cut demarcation between the sacred and the profane. The line between sacred and profane is often fluid, not rigid. There is interconnectedness of all things which upholds the Ubuntu philosophy "I am because we are and because we are, therefore I am" The spirits (sacred) interact with the humans (profane) in their daily life. The Orishas (sacred) in Yoruba influence farming (profane). In the Igbo New Yam Festival, the ancestors and humans share in the food and community feast. Ifemesia (1979) says Igbo cosmology sees no strict divide, spirits inhabit both realms. It is for this that nature and the environment are held sacred and the deities or spirits are revered.

Practices

These are group of activities like ceremonies, festivals, rituals, rites, libations and offerings etc that show how Africans express their beliefs in practical terms. Through all these means, they venerate and honour their ancestors and the divinities or spirits. like Orisha, Amadioha, Anyanwu. Through divination and spiritual guidance, traditional healing and medicine are enacted. These traditional rituals and ceremonies promote environmental, fostering community-based decision making and governance. This aspect ensures balance and reciprocity as it lays emphasis on collective well being and social cohesion.

Values System

This aspect of the religion covers the people's notion of what truth, justice, right and wrong, love, good and evil, beauty, respect for people and property, crime and punishment, praise and blame should be. This has to do with human interconnectedness and the community. It also advocates for individual and collective well being of the community through balance and reciprocity in relationships, respect for elders and tradition and harmony with nature and the environment.

3 Sustainable Development

This refers to the process of meeting the requisite needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet their own needs. It encompasses economic, social and environmental dimensions aimed at a balance that promotes long-term well being and prosperity. Eliot (1971) argues that there is no agreement as to what constitutes development. It was coined by developed nations to describe the powerful and powerless nations. Onwuliri (2008) observes that there are various aspects to what development is. However, common to all these is a positive change in human well being. The individual and his quality of life must be the centre of the idea of development. African religion is very emphatic on this. In African religion, the desire for life and its preservation is summum bonum, that is, the greatest good and everything humanly possible must be done to ensure its realization. Levi and Havinden (1982) comprehend it as a long term improvement in the standard of living as felt and judged to be by many people in the country.

4 Linking ATR Tenets to SDGs

In the past, economists saw development primarily from the perspective or prism of economic growth. In that context, so long as the monetary value of goods and services (Gross Domestic Product) increased yearly, there was development. But Nwajiuba (1999) objects to this perspective as false, as there could be an economic growth without development, that is, if the majority of the people did not benefit from it. Onwuliri (2008) further recalls that development goes beyond the narrow lines of economic and material advancement. Development is a multidimensional process involving the totality of man in his political, economic, psychological and social relations among others. To Asumah (2010), development is a process of reaching self-sufficiency, self-reliance and advancement. Development may include growth, but growth itself is not a necessary condition for development. Growth itself is an increase in productivity measured in gross national product (GNP), gross domestic product (GDP) or physical quality of life index (PQLI). The ATR tenets can inspire culturally rooted solutions for sustainable development. Reverence for nature which is seen from environmental ethics may be aligned with SDG 13 (climate Action) throwing up the case of Ghana's sacred groves eg Asumang-Kwame shrine protected by traditional priests. These forests conserve biodiversity, sequester carbon and prevent soil erosion. Also, reverence for nature is seen in life on land linked to SDG 15 which talks about protecting biodiversity through taboos on hunting certain animals eg totemic animals in Nigeria. In African Religion, the people's reverence for nature aligns with climate mitigation. On the other hand, ancestral veneration marked by peace and justice and linked to SDG 16 shows Nigeria's Igbo 'og-buefi' system resolves land disputes through ancestral mediation, reducing communal conflicts, veneration of ancestors guides fair, consensus driven justice. Ancestor based conflict resolution eg Ghana's 'dugbe' system fosters social cohesion. Also, the preservation of cultural heritage sites linked to SDG 11 in sustainable cities eg ancestral shrines boosts community identity and tourism. Communal Ethics which drives South Africa's ubuntu based cooperatives and reduced inequalities linked to SDG 10 eg women led farming collectives promote equitable resource sharing, thereby empowering marginalized people. Partnerships linked to SDG 17 emphasize community collaboration which strengthens local governance and partnerships for development.

5 Innovation

The term innovation involves creating something new, such as new ideas, products, services or processes that improve lives and address challenges. It drives technological progress, increasing efficiency, productivity and competitiveness. Innovation can also address social challenges such as poverty, inequality and access to healthcare. African religion and innovation intersect in various ways, driving development and progress on the continent. For instance, African traditional medicine has been a cornerstone of healthcare in many African communities, with practitioners using innovative methods to treat illnesses and promote well being. Researchers in African religion are also exploring ways to integrate traditional medicine with modern healthcare systems, thereby improving access to quality healthcare. African religion is being recognized as a viable option for sustainable development with interfaith collaboration and dialogue promoting unity and progress. African religious leaders are leveraging innovation to address social challenges, promote sustainable development and foster community growth.

6 Demonstrating Innovation in Nation Building

African traditional religion (ATR) has contributed to innovations in several ways. ATR has contributed to social innovations through emphasis on community and collective well-being which inspires social entrepreneurship and community-led initiatives. Traditional conflict resolution mechanisms ensure modern peace building and mediation efforts. Example, the ubuntu-based stokvel savings clubs in South Africa promote community savings and microfinance, empowering women and reducing poverty.

In the area of technological innovations, ATR contributes to traditional knowledge systems which ensure sustainable agriculture, environmental conservation and natural resource management. Indigenous medicine and healing practices which are products of African religion contribute to development of new medicines and therapies. Example: In Ghana, Dr Nana app combines traditional herbal medicine with AI, to offer personalized health advice and connect users to herbalists.

Also in governance innovations, traditional leadership structures and participatory decision-making processes engender inclusive governance models. Ubuntu philosophy which emphasizes the interconnectedness of beings and community shapes people-centred policy making. Example, in Rwanda, the imihigo performance contracts, inspired by traditional accountability systems, improves local governance and service delivery. These ATR principles foster community-based solutions, blending tradition with modernity.

The impact of Nigeria's evolving religious landscape on nation building can be seen in its ability to foster social cohesion. Syncretism brings about interfaith dialogue e.g. joint festivals like Durbar blend Islam with ATR but tensions such as Boko Haram targeting ATR shrines labeling them idolatry fuel divisions. Pentecostal churches clash with traditional rulers over demonization of ATR. It promotes cultural identity for instance, ATR-infused practices e.g. Osun Oshogbo festival, New Yam festival etc boost cultural pride, tourism and national heritage. But puritanical groups reject ATR as backward.

7 ATR, Modernity and Religious Syncretism

In Nigeria, African traditional religion values persist or are integrated within Christian and Islamic practices through the processes of religious syncretism. In Christianity for instance, the Aladura churches e.g. Cherubim and Seraphim incorporate ATR elements like ancestors, prayers, drumming and herbal healing. Some Pentecostal churches fear ancestral spirits but unconsciously retain ATR worldviews e.g. spiritual causality. Aladura churches use ATR inspired "holy water" mixed with local herbs for healing, syncretizing Christian prayer with traditional rituals. Visionary prophets claim ancestral spirits guide them thereby syncretizing ATR divination.

In Islam, the Bori cults syncretizes Islam with ATR spirit possession rituals and herbalism. Sufi orders e.g. Tijaniyya incorporate local customs like Salla festivals thereby merging ATR communalism with Is-

lamic practices. Their adaptation mechanisms can be seen in their parallel practices, symbolic integration and reinterpretation e.g. Christians and Muslims attend churches and mosques but still consult Babalawos (Ifa priests) for guidance. Churches use traditional symbols e.g. kolanuts in communion while mosques adopt local architectural styles. ATR concepts like ancestors as intermediaries parallel Christian saints or Islamic wali saints.

The persistence of African traditional religion values is etched in communal ethics based on ubuntu philosophy. In this sense, church and mosque gatherings emphasize community welfare. Christians and Muslims secretly perform ATR rituals at home. The Osun Oshogbo cultural festival attracts tourists from all over the world, thereby legitimizing African traditional religion. However, as it poses governance challenges such as Sharia laws in northern Nigeria and secular constitutions in southern Nigeria, ATR rights e.g. shrine protection and anti-idolatry laws, it provides policy making opportunities e.g. Federal Character principle in balancing representation e.g. ATR holidays like Ojude Oba in Yoruba alongside Christian and Muslim ones. Its nation building potential lies in leveraging syncretism for unity e.g. the campaigns for one Nigeria highlighting shared rituals e.g. communal Ramadan, Easter, Ifa festivals and recognizing ATR heritage in inclusive policies in education, media and governance. Syncretism bridges divides but extremism hinders it.

To demonstrate the practical relevance of African Traditional Religion to sustainable development, two empirical examples or case studies are relevant here:

Community Dispute Resolution through Traditional Oath-Taking: In Nigeria, traditional oath-taking is still used to settle various cases especially theft and land disputes and to promote community peace. For instance, the Igbo Igiri Iwu Oath-Taking Ceremony, which involves swearing before ancestral spirits, ensuring truthful testimony and deterring false claims. This practice reduces court cases and fosters social cohesion.

Environmental Conservation through Sacred Grove Practices: The Osun Oshogbo Sacred Grove in Nigeria, a UNESCO World Heritage Site showcases ATR's role in conservation. Taboos prohibit hunting, fishing and tree-cutting thereby preserving biodiversity. This way, over 400 plant species and endangered monkeys have been protected. In like manner, community led patrols and rituals protect the grove, combining cultural heritage with ecosystem preservation.

On the other hand, African Traditional Religion mechanisms and institutions instill and enforce moral values e.g. Age Grade Systems in Nigeria like the Otu Ogbo Age Grade Societies in Igbo land and other youth groups organized by age perform communal tasks e.g. cleaning, clearing bush paths, providing security, teaching responsibility and solidarity. They foster discipline and respect for elders and render community service. In Kenya, the Morans, that is, Maasai warriors now mobilize for climate action e.g. tree planting campaigns and also create HIV/AIDS awareness. They blend tradition with climate action SDG 13.

Masquerade institutions also enforce moral values e.g. in the Yoruba Egungun masquerade institution, the masqueraders embody ancestors enforcing norms through masked performances. Misbehavior or crimes like theft lead to Egungun sanctions such as fines, public shaming etc. This institution instills accountability and fear of ancestral wrath. The Eyo Masquerade festival in Lagos promotes cultural tourism.

Ancestral Sanctions also enforce moral values e.g. in Akan tradition in Ghana, the stool councils now partner with NGOs to protect sacred groves e.g. Boabeng Fiema Monkey Sanctuary. Ancestral taboos enforce conservation. This protects life on land SDG 15. Ancestral spirits sanction misconducts such as land grabbing through dreams, illness or crop failure. Offenders must appease the ancestors through rituals. Ancestral sanctions maintain respect for tradition and consequences for breaking taboos.

ATR Mechanisms could as well be adapted to enhance modern governance framework. Youths in the age grade system could be mobilized for civic engagements like voter registration exercise and community policing e.g. the Otu Ogbo Age Grade in Nigeria could partner with local government for security SDG 16. The masquerade institutions could use cultural diplomacy and tourism to brand festivals like Eyo Festival, Egungun festival as peace ambassadors for inter ethnic dialogue. They could be used to mediate communal conflicts. Ancestral sanctions could serve as environmental laws through sacred grove protection. Governments could as well recognize ATR protected lands e.g. Ghana's CREMA framework, the Maasai lands

in Kenya managed through customary laws. Secret Societies could collaborate with governments on justice e.g. the Ekpe secret society should aid the fight against corruption through anonymous tips. But they should ensure transparency and avoid human rights abuse. Constitutional recognition could be accorded ATR mechanisms by including ATR councils in Nigeria's National Assembly e.g. House of Chiefs. Hybrid courts could be instituted where traditional mediation e.g. Igbo land Ala courts are blended with formal systems. Cultural governance could also be incentivized e.g. granting tax breaks to communities for preserving sacred sites e.g. Osun Oshogbo sacred site.

8 Nation Building

Nation building is the process of creating and strengthening a nation's identity, institutions and social cohesion. It promotes a shared sense of belonging, purpose and values among citizens. It also involves the strengthening of government, healthcare, education and other institutions that support a nation's development. Nation building addresses social inequalities, promotes tolerance and builds bridges between different communities.

Based specifically on African context, Rivkin (1969) says nation building in Africa is a process of defining the geographic area in which a particular state is to be built and developing the constitutional structure to give the state form and shape, the political system to give it life and provide the name for the population to relate to the state and the economy to sustain the state structure and political system—all with a view to welding the multiple, disparate, non-cohesive and unrelated population groups to be found in all the new states of Africa into identifiable and integrated nations within their respective borders. For Rivkin, the issue of the delimitation of territorial boundaries is very crucial in the process of nation building. To him, so long as some wider units is conceived of as the one to which loyalty and allegiance is due, the focus and concentration on building, for instance a Nigerian, Congolese, Ghanaian and other nations in Africa will be badly diffused. Until there is definition as to area, it is difficult, if not impossible to cope effectively with nation building. From the diverse views of nation building so far, we have seen that the major ingredient or element in nation building is the desire and effort to achieve unity among the multi-ethnic groups within a state.

9 Contributions of African Religion to Nation Building

African countries are converging at a very fast rate with the west, yet, they remain underdeveloped according to the measures of development. In view of this, African religion has a lot of contributions to offer to African countries in terms of sustainable development and innovation in nation building. African religion plays a formidable role in diverse areas such as social cohesion, morality and discipline, conflict resolution among others which African leaders, both secular and religious, administrators, organizations and institutions can harness for corporate wellbeing and sustainable development.

Morality and Discipline: In African religion, the cult of ancestors is at the heart of African ontological belief. There is a strong tie between the present life and the hereafter. The life of men in the present defines their life in the hereafter. To buttress this point, Nweke and Nwoye (2014) asserts that it is the belief and desire of an average African to belong to the cult of ancestors in order to have the power to reincarnate and influence the living in the hereafter. Apart from other virtues which an African must possess in order to belong to this cult after life is a high sense of morality. Consequently, every man strived to lead a life that culminates in morality. In view of this, Ezeanya (1980) maintains that to gain the hereafter as a place of enjoyment, man must behave in ways consonant with the endless demands of the divinities and ancestors. Above all, he must ensure that his behaviour does not precipitate calamity not only for himself and his family, but also for the society at large. (p. 331). So, in the past, when there was a rapport between men and supernatural powers and when there were no policemen to provide security, the close watch of the divinities and ancestors on men in traditional African societies became a source of order and security that prevailed

at that time. For Nweke and Nwoye (2014), crime and evil deeds rip the society apart and no society torn apart by evil and crime can develop. Morality serves as a regulatory factor that holds other aspects of human behaviour in check. If Africans can embrace this unique sense of morality couched in the ancestral cult, which abhors all forms of conceivable and perceivable crime and evil practices, Africa will definitely return to the path of sustainable development.

African nations grapple with a lot of moral issues such as corrupt leadership, embezzlement of public fund, bribery and corruption, indiscipline, *yahoo yahoo* among others which have continued to cripple their national development. Insecurity caused by banditry, insurgency and kidnappings has even become a bigger threat to Nigeria's national development. If African countries can bring back the tenets of African Traditional Religion, development in Africa will not only be progressive, it will be sustained. African religion emphasizes the importance of morality and discipline which are crucial for sustainable development. Morality engenders and sustains discipline and discipline enables an individual and by extension a nation to attain the greatest good in the developmental process. By promoting values such as honesty, integrity and hard work, religion can help individuals and communities develop a strong moral foundation which is a very powerful need for development.

Social Cohesion: African religious values promote unity and cooperation, which are essential for nation building. By fostering a sense of community and shared identity, African religion helps bring people together and promote social cohesion. Agbo (2011) recognizes this fact when he stated that Africans have an economic system that embodies a capitalist orientation cum a socialist one in addition to welfarist policy. This system founded on African communism or communalism is different from other forms of communalism. It is distinct in the sense that it is a communalism that recognizes individual freedom and the community life of African people. Emphasizing on the individuality of the African in his community life, Onyibor (2007) asserts that the individual in African community is not only a community man, but also a distinct individual entity with his free will and responsibility. The individual is free so far as his liberty does not interfere with the affairs of the corporate entity or community. However, the conception of the individual as a distinct entity as well as a community man is fundamentally based on ontology. Individuality in this African system is different from the western type. Ogugua (2007) further clarifies this by saying that the west is a collectivist kind of society. This means that every individual is autonomous, on his own, separate from every other individual. On the other hand, African society is a community; the African puts more stress on the solidarity of the group and on the communion of the members than on the autonomy and contributions and needs of the individual. There is also a sense of justice in African communal system of life. As articulated by Ekei (2001), justice in African communalism entails a constant integration of individuals into communal existence and relationships. It is in this context of human cooperation, coexistence and communalism that the obvious limitations of nature such as human needs, scarcity, inequality, powerlessness as well as human contingencies could be addressed or taken care of. Justice in communalism through collective integration tries to minimize individual tendencies towards excessive egoism and self-seeking. This collective aspiration seems to take the place of war of one against all. It assists the individual to see himself as not at war with others, but as part and parcel of the community. African communalism which is one of the fundamental values of African religion fosters social cohesion which is important for the development African nations.

Conflict Resolution: Conflict brings about instability, bitterness and rancour which stifles development. Conflict has created banditry and terrorism which have punctured the growth and development of African nations. For instance, it has impacted severely on Nigeria's growth and development, manifesting in various forms such as banditry and terrorism. In an expression of worry, Ezechi (2016) says Africa's growth is bedeviled by conflicts, crises, tensions and in the extreme, wars and terrorism. (p. 25). Book Haram's insurgency which started in 2009 has been a major driver of instability, causing widespread displacement, violence and disrupting economic activities. The group's activities have led to significant human suffering with thousands killed, injured or abducted. In response to this, African religion can contribute significantly to the resolution of these conflicts that have disrupted peace building and retarded development. The Ubuntu philosophy which emphasizes the interconnectedness of human beings irrespective of where we come from in Africa is an example of African value that can promote peace and development. This could also be likened

to Julius Nyerere's Ujamaa philosophy which envisioned a society composed of atomic family units. In Nyerere's ideology or blueprint as cited by Ezechi (2016), Tanzania was to become a country made up of Ujamaa villages with mutual cooperation and collaboration. The nation would be fundamentally made up of family units embracing the whole society by extension.

This Ujamaa ideology is characterized by distributionism as distinguished from the acquisitionism of the capitalist society. Onwubiko (1991) further explains that Ujamaa means "togetherness" or "familyhood". It is not a familyhood founded on consanguinity but on community spirit of togetherness which considers all peoples as brothers. In it, the welfare of each individual becomes the direct concern of the members of the clan. Africans can count on the community spirit generated by these two ideologies (community consciousness and Ujamaa) to forge an unprecedented advancement in the continent. The community spirit assists in the gradual growth of the community by making the community and its members more technologically and economically advanced. This community spirit creates avenue for community developmental projects such as building of schools, town halls, community hospitals or healthcare centres, microfinance banks, provision of electricity and pipe borne water which can be extended to national and continental levels. Through these viable ideologies, many African communities can rely on traditional religious leaders and practices to resolve disputes and promote peace and unity.

Governance: African religion can also contribute to governance, particularly in areas where the state is weak or absent. In some cases, religious leaders and networks have taken on roles that would normally be filled by the state such as providing security and social services. Davis (cited by Ezechi, 2016) states that governance is all about leadership because the success or otherwise of leadership has a domino effect on the followership. To him, human beings are the most precious part of civilization. What then could be more important than the leadership and development of people? Without leadership, an organization is but a muddle of men and machines. Leadership is the human factor which binds a group together and motivates it towards goal attainment. Unfortunately, good governance which could have taken Africa to the level of advanced countries has been bedeviled and characterized by bribery and corruption, embezzlement of public funds, corrupt leadership and all forms of malpractice. Governance all over Africa has been badly brutalized, butchered and smeared by corruption. As Ezechi (2016) put it, the backwardness of Africa in terms of technological advancement and infrastructural development is to a very large extent as a result of the seemingly endemic corruption in most government quarters. When the funds meant for development are siphoned through private accounts of the leaders or through their proxies, the effect is obviously the collapse or retardation of the economy. Donald Duke, the former governor of Cross River State (cited by Ezechi, 2016) says there are two aspects of corruption. There is the corruption that is caused by lack of opportunity. When you lack opportunities, it amounts to survival of the fittest. There is that which is driven by greed. That is where the elites and those in authority come in.

As Duke rightly pointed out, corruption is as a result of either lack of opportunity or greed. In this regard, governance or leadership is at the centre of this argument, since it is the responsibility of the government to provide enabling environment for opportunities to evolve. He further explained that when someone in a position of trust confiscates the resources of the people entrusted into his care for personal use, then it is not just corruption, it is outright crime. They say corruption is a crime, but it is as criminal as robbery. As a matter of fact, with corruption all over the continent, the hope of Africa being at par with developed countries is a far cry. This is where African religious value of oath taking offers a solution. As a very important value that needs to be revived, Ugwu (2001) regretted that the very important instrument of detecting culprits in the Nigerian society (oath taking) has been discarded with the advent of foreign religions. People now take oath according to their religious inclination and no longer on the basis of their original rich cultural heritage. This undoubtedly has provided room for moral decadence and other vices in our social system by committing atrocious crimes and yet getting free from such acts without being penalized. When politicians take oath of office, they should be made to swear by African gods. Let them leave the Bible or Koran alone. They should use cutlass because we believe that that will be more effective. Let them swear to the kind of oath our culture provides for, then we will see who would do something wrong. In the past, people were more honest. One would not need to stay with one's wares when selling them. Customers would make the

correct payment for goods even when nobody was there to watch them.

Omenani is another very important value thrown up by African religion which could contribute to the wellbeing and overall development of Africa. Edeh (1985) urges Africans to align with *omenani* as antidote to vice and disunity. He maintains that *omenani* is an inherited pattern of thought and action that is mysteriously in harmony with the totality of all that is. For further clarification, we must add that *omenani* is a generic term for the body of Igbo socio-religious laws, customs and traditions passed down from generation to generation and handed down to the ancestors by God through the Earthgod. Any act which is opposed to the good of man and community is anti-*omenani* and by extension antithetical to unity in Africa. All sorts of undesirable occurrences in the universe are regarded as evil because they disrupt the normal order of reality which is supposed to be preserved by *omenani*. Social offences are regarded as *aru*, that is, a pollution or abomination against the Earthgod. This is a clear indication that African tradition is equally key to continental unity and development which only requires the will of Africans to cherish by avoiding evil and doing good.

Speaking further on security governance, Arase (cited by Olanrewaju, 2018) established that the concept of community-based policing which is closely interlinked with social and religious structures is a product of the African culture that had been in practice in local communities long before the advent of colonialism and was highly effective in maintaining law and order largely without the use of violence. He said that community-based policing and social control architecture was woven around the traditional institutions and customs and were visible among the Yorubas in the Southwest and the Hausas in the Northern part of Nigeria, pointing out that these traditional community policing practices varied in orientation and implementation and were known to share the modern principles associated with community policing as being advanced by the western world just as they were very effective in enabling the pre-colonial Nigerian societies in security governance.

Acholonu (cited by Ezeani, 2013) wishes that Nigerians and by extension Africans could learn from the Igbo traditional philosophies of life when he stated that Ndigbo happen to be among the few groups of people in the world whose core traditional philosophies of life consist of virtues rather than vices, that is, justice and fair play (*ikpe kwu oto*), impeccability (*ikwuba aka oto* or *ijide ogu*), peace and the brotherhood of man (*onyebiri ibe ya biri*), right action and right judgement (*ofo na ogu* or *ome ihe jide ofo*), right is might (*ofo ka nsi*). Based on these philosophies of life, it has been acknowledged that it was the Igbo people who through their individual efforts have more than any other group of people in Nigeria, developed different parts of Nigeria. This they have done even at the neglect of their own states in Igbo land. They build modern houses and modern market stalls in different parts of Nigeria especially in the North and Lagos. Some state governments in the North and West have long realized that this could be exploited. That the Igbo people are nation builders seems obvious, though not many other Nigerians acknowledge this fact. All these were borne out of their traditional religious belief in justice, fair play and brotherhood of man. However, African religious symbols which are an aspect of African religion have contributed immensely to industrial development. Kanu (2014) acknowledges that these symbols are adapted for textile designs. African symbols are found on many interior decorations, wall hangings and fashion designs. These symbols are used by cottage industries, paint and dyes and cotton growers. If this is well harnessed, it could create more employment and a means for revenue generation. It could as well boost tourism. People all over the world want to see new things and African religious symbols can satisfy their curiosity.

10 Addressing Negative Perceptions of ATR

ATR is associated with prevailing stereotypes or misconceptions such as superstition, witchcraft, demonic, anti-progress or modernity and so on. However, ATR cannot be superstitious or primitive because it is a complex religion with deep philosophies like the Ifa cosmology in Yoruba. Like every other religion, ATR uses symbolism e.g. divination. Moreover, the recognition of the Osun Oshogbo Cultural Festival on global scale as heritage by UNESCO validates ATR's cultural values. People also misconceive ATR as witchcraft.

Witchcraft like juju is a separate practice often politicized. ATR emphasizes ethics not witchcraft which is seen in the Omoluabi Code in Yoruba advocates for honesty, humility etc. but media sensationalism like witch hunts in Northern Ghana distorts ATR. Furthermore, African Traditional Religion is neither anti-progress nor anti-modernity. For instance, it adapts digital evangelism by priests, sacred groves protected by ATR preserve biodiversity. But Pentecostal deliverance crusades burn shrines, erasing cultural heritage. ATR is not demonic. It is the Christians and Muslims that describe it so. Moreover, the interfaith dialogue shows that ATR's respect for creation aligns with Abrahamic values. Yet, colonialism labeled ATR pagan, justifying exploitation by slave trade. To Address these issues of stereotypes, the government should include ATR in schools e.g. Nigeria's curriculum reform. The media instead of its destructive criticism, should document ATR's positive roles e.g. conflict resolution through oath taking, conservation of biodiversity etc. In addition, governments could enact laws against witch hunting like Ghana's 2014 Witchcraft Act.

11 Strategies to Promote ATR's Positive Role in Nation Building

In order to effectively counter the negative perceptions about ATR, so as to promote its positive contributions to nation building, these strategies have been adopted.

1. There should be Interdisciplinary Research collaboration between Religious Studies and Sociology to document ATR's role in peace building e.g. resolving of land disputes through oath taking. Case studies could as well be carried out in order to learn about Osun Oshogbo eco-tourism or Igbo age grades aiding public health.
2. African Studies Association conferences should host panel discussions on ATR and Nation Building. Policymakers such as Nigeria's Ministry of Culture should invited to co-organize.
3. Publications in journals like African Affairs or Journal of Religion in Africa should feature ATR's modern relevance. Edited volumes should about ATR and Sustainable Development.

The Educational Strategies are:

1. Curriculum reform should include ATR in Nigerian schools. At secondary school level, it should be ATR's Role Pre-Colonial Governance. At the tertiary level, courses like ATR and Interfaith Dialogue should be introduced.
2. There should be Digital Outreach to people e.g. ATR Insights on Spotify, debunk myths e.g. ATR and Witchcraft, Short Documentaries YouTube like Sacred Groves and Climate Action e.g. Ghana's CREMA.
3. There should be community engagement on workshops to train ATR priests as peace ambassadors e.g. mediating farmer-herder conflicts. Universities should partner with ATR councils e.g. Ooni of Ife or Obi of Onitsha for joint projects.

12 Conclusion

African religion has the potential to make significant contributions to sustainable development and innovation in nation building by promoting moral values, community cohesion, environmental conservation, education, healthcare, peace and economic development. By working together with governments and other stakeholders, African religious institutions can help to build a more sustainable and prosperous future for Africa. By understanding the contributions and challenges of African religion, policy makers and development practitioners can work more effectively with religious communities to promote development and

reduce poverty. Also, by leveraging the influence and resources of African religion, it is very much possible to make significant progress in conflict resolution which is key to peaceful coexistence among diverse communities for innovative and sustainable development.

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